

METHODS OF DEVELOPING THE LOGICAL THINKING SKILLS OF LEARNERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14543510>

Abstract. *The given article presents the discussion of different methods, aimed at developing students' logical thinking skills. It provides the ability to think logically, apply acquired knowledge and solve problems in new situations. It also provides methods for stimulating thinking through interactive lessons, games and group work. It also discusses activities that help improve logical dilemma solving and critical thinking skills. Besides that, the article describes the methods for solving and testing problems in different contexts to develop students' analytical thinking. These approaches are designed to make future educational processes more effective.*

Keywords: *logical Thinking, Students, Development Methods, Interactive Lessons, Group Work, Analytical Thinking, Problem Solving, Games, Dilemma, Cognitive Skills, Learning Process, Critical Thinking, Problem Solving, Teaching Methods, Ways to Develop Logical Thinking Skills in Students.*

It is important to suggest that logical thinking is the ability of a person, aimed at the solution of problems, drawing logical conclusions and expressing thoughts clearly. Developing the logical thinking skills of students will help them to succeed in the general education process. The given research discusses particular ways to develop logical thinking skills. They are the followings:

Logic Games and Puzzles: Logic games and puzzles are very useful for students. Such games require logical thinking, analysis, and problem solving. For example, chess, sudoku, logic puzzles, etc.

Exploration and Problem Solving: Providing students with various problem solving tasks and encouraging them to explore helps develop logical thinking skills. Students improve their thinking skills by identifying problems, analyzing them, and developing solutions.

Regular Discussions: Regular discussions in the classroom develop students ability to express their opinions, reason, and exchange ideas with others. This process helps students develop a deeper understanding of logical thinking.

Encouraging Creative Thinking: It is also important to develop creative thinking in students. Encouraging them to come up with new ideas, find innovative solutions, and express their thoughts freely helps strengthen logical thinking.

Analyzing a topic: Asking students to analyze a topic helps them develop their analysis and synthesis skills. This process increases students' ability to form their own thoughts and draw logical conclusions. **Importance of the teacher's role:** Teachers develop students' logical thinking skills.

According to the National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan, Integral is one of the basic concepts of mathematical analysis. Integration is the process of finding an indefinite integral in mathematics. Integration is the process of bringing together and interacting disciplines, going hand in hand with differentiation.

In the Macmillan English Dictionary for Advanced Learners, anyone can find the following explanations:

1. Rounding off a part for making the sentence complete;
2. Combining two or more things into a single system or part.

Definitely, integration is the unification of things, people or different thoughts into one. According to scientists, the term "pedagogical integration" implies explaining and predicting specific forms of integration and managing them in accordance with the tasks of pedagogy. V. Bezrukova confirms this rule and characterizes it as a type of scientific integration implemented within the framework of pedagogical theory and practice. Integration in pedagogical research is described as "integrity, systemicity, interdependence, complexity"; "principle, process and result"; "unification of disparate parts into a whole", "complexification and summation" synthesized courses and interdisciplinary connections".

However, these characteristics do not fully reflect the uniqueness of integration as a pedagogical phenomenon. A. Yu. Danilyuk believes that the reasons for this case are the followings:

- 1) perception of integration, limited productivity;
- 2) technological failure of the event;
- 3) non-understanding of integration as a dialectical, self-organizing process;
- 4) opposition of integration and differentiation.

Certainly, the researcher emphasizes the dialectic of the interconnectedness of these phenomena: knowledge was initially differentiated by different subjects, in fact, this gives rise to the need for integration, differentiation is the beginning of integration. It is wrong to completely contrast two dialectically intersecting phenomena: differentiation is the starting point of integration, therefore the result of integration should be the beginning of differentiation. Integration in education is widely studied. According to the scientists ideas provided by Prof. R. Mavlonova and Prof. N. Rakhmonkulova [90], in the source "Integrated Pedagogy of Primary Education", there was suggested about the effectiveness of teaching mathematics through the interdisciplinary communication, there were explained the reason of paying particular attention to the problem of integrated education at present time especially in the methodological-didactic foundations of primary education due to ideas provided by Prof. B. Abdullaeva, theoretical foundations of the creative organization regarding primary education and Prof. B. Adizov, who provided particular information regarding primary school and pedagogical conditions for developing the speed of students thinking skills, which ere studied by Prof. O. Aslonova.

Besides that, the didactic foundations of the formation of students cognitive activity were studied by Prof. R. Ibragimov, Prof. M. Gulyamova [74], aimed at developing interpersonal skills of learners regarding personal, social, economic and professional relationships, which are aimed at being able to create own place in society, solve the possible problems, have a broad worldview and knowledge in all aspects, first of all, everyone must acquire particular types of sciences. In order to integrate education, to participate in mutual communication in society, it is necessary to develop the competence of language proficiency and the ability to use it effectively, especially in communication, that leads to the development of a communicative competence.

1. According to the definition proposed by Podlas, "integration is the process and result of forming a whole, based on identifying important connections between relatively independent parts and individual scientific disciplines". The goal of integration is understood as "unification of knowledge", unification of various areas of knowledge, as well as giving information a certain density, as well as separation of the most valuable and important concepts. Researchers emphasize that as a result of introducing integrated subjects into the educational process, it is possible to "form and develop generalized knowledge, which, in turn, contributes to the

formation of holistic thinking and consciousness". The goal of integration is "unification of knowledge", combining various areas of knowledge, as well as compressing information in a certain sense, the most valuable and important aspect is the separation of aspects. As a result of introducing integrated subjects into the educational process, "there is an opportunity to develop generalized knowledge, which, in turn, promotes the formation of holistic thinking and consciousness". A.Yu. Danylyuk notes that the concept of integration has been introduced into the context of pedagogy, but insufficient pedagogical content does not allow us to speak of it as a sufficiently substantiated scientific and pedagogical concept. Classification and integration of scientific knowledge reflect two unique processes of cognition.

Definitely, the relationship between the abstract and the concrete is expressed at two levels: the transition from the concrete to the abstract (differentiation) and learning from the abstract to the concrete (integration). Precisely, because it is a synthesis of many definitions, precisely because of its generality and versatility. In thinking, it therefore serves as a process of synthesis. At present time 70 percent of the world's countries use integrated curricula and textbooks in their education system. All countries are the same.

Depending on the nature of the order placed in the education system of a given country, various levels of subject integration, integrated sciences have been developed and implemented in Australia, Japan, Northern Ireland, Wales. In Hong Kong and Germany, individual subjects, in Hungary, subjects in the direction of "Culture, Man and Nature" are integrated subjects, in the Netherlands - individual subjects, in Ireland, all subjects are taught comprehensively.

By summerising it should be suggested that didactic features of the integrated technology for increasing the effectiveness of primary education (focus on the student's personality, management of educational activities, concentration, cooperation, creativity) subject matter, basic concepts and knowledge, skills and abilities, clarification of qualifications based on ensuring the dynamic integration of competencies with educational goals (educational, upbringing, developmental) are implemented in the works of N. Abdullayeva.

REFERENCES

1. Akhmedova N. Improving the professional training of future teachers based on an integrative approach. A dissertation was written for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences. Tashkent 2020. 161 p.
2. Aslonova O. Pedagogical conditions for the formation of the speed of thinking in primary school students. Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD) diss. Against, 2020
3. Akhmedova L.B. Development of didactic and methodological competence of future primary school teachers. Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) Dissertation in Pedagogical Sciences. Tashkent 2022
4. Botirova N.L. Development of educational activities of future primary school teachers. The dissertation was written for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences. Tashkent-2022.